

Changes in the Properties of Luvisols, Planosols and Fluvisols Under the Influence of Agroproduction Activity from the Region of Sofia District

Ivaylo Kirilov, Vanya Lozanova, Iliana Gerasimova,
Vesselin Pankov

*“Nikola Poushkarov” Institute of Soil Science,
Agrotechnologies and Plant Protection, Bulgaria, Sofia 1331,
7 Shosse Bankya str.*

Corresponding Author: Ivaylo Kirilov, e-mail: stingra@abv.bg

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Abstract

The soils from the Dolna Banya valley of Sofia district are formed under forest meadow, bush and tree vegetation. It has influenced their texture, natural fertility and the reaction of the soil solution. As they are located in a semi-mountainous terrain, surface horizons are subject to erosion processes and podzolization.

The aim of the research is to establish the changes in the profile of Rhodic Luvisols which occurred as a result of natural influences and the type of production activity on them.

The research has found that for a long time there have been changes in the surface soil horizons of all studied differences of Rhodic Luvisols. The process of podzolization continues to develop and there is an increase in the content of silt in the horizons below the humus horizon. In the case of Fluvisols, an increase in the fraction of coarse and fine sand is reported. In the case of moderately eroded Planosols land use has an impact on the soil texture. In the deeper horizons, when planted with raspberries, the content of silt and physical clay increases compared to the same soil difference in the area with the application of three-field crop rotation, compacted with cereals using a shallow mouldboard ploughing .

Keywords: Fluvisols, Luvisols, Planosols, Sofia district, process of pseudopodzolization, soil texture, three-field crop rotation

Introduction

From the fact that the properties of the soils and the degree of their fertility depend a lot on the type and age of the parent rocks, on the relief, exposure, latitude and altitude, as well as on the climatic conditions that activate or suppress more or less biological activity, the state and biological potential of soil differences are determined (Teoharov 2004; Blum, 2007; Kinoshita et al., 2017). This feature of the soil formation process is an objective basis for the action of the third law of agriculture: "for the unity and interdependence of growth and development of plant associations and their habitat" from which arises the objective need for an ecological approach in organizing and managing production in crop production (Krastanov, 2006; Ugarte et al., 2016).

The soils from the Dolna Banya valley are formed under forest meadow, bush and tree vegetation, which has affected their texture, natural fertility and the reaction of the soil

solution (Koynov et al., 1972; Penkov et al., 1985; Ninov et al., 1985; Boneva et al., 2005; *IUSS Working Group*, 2015; Teoharov et al., 2019).

As they are located on a semi-mountainous terrain characterized by rough terrain with ravines and gullies that have slope 8-10⁰ and the soil surface horizons are subject to erosion processes and pseudopodzolization. The climate is transition continental region of the European continental climate and is temperate continental influenced by the river valley of Maritsa river and its tributaries (Boneva et al., 2005; Ninov, 2007).

Economic activity in the past was determined by the cultivation of cereals, fiber crops, potatoes and mainly berry crops, natural and artificial pastures and meadows.

The aim of the research is to establish the changes in the profiles of Luvisols, Fluvisols and Planosols which occurred as a result of natural influences and the type of land use on them.

Materials and Methods

The subject of the study are the following differences of soils:

Rhodic Luvisols, slightly eroded.

They are distributed in the form of individual spots in the southeastern and northeastern part of the land. They occupy an area of 3875 da - which represents 2.39% of the total area. They are formed on non-carbonate weathering products under the influence of forest vegetation. As a result of the recent slight erosion, part of the light surface horizon has been removed, due to which the profile is somewhat shortened. The profile is clearly differentiated. Most of the area of the considered soil differences is included in the arable fund of the farm units. An idea of the morphological structure of these soils is given by the description of profiles made one kilometer northeast of the village of Pchelin (Yolevski, M. et al. 1974).

A₁B fallow land 0- 20 yellowish-brown (7.5YR/5/4 in the dry state), fresh, compacted, clayey-sandy, granular and crumbly structure, does not carbonate from hydrochloric acid, transition noticeable.

B_{1t} 20- 36 reddish-brown (5YR/3.5/ 6 in dry state), rusty-reddish spots, slightly moistened, dense, medium sandy-clayey, prismatic-lumpy structure, not carbonated by hydrochloric acid, transition noticeable.

B_{2t} 36- 54 reddish-brown (5YR/3/6 in the dry state), rusty-reddish spots, moist, dense, medium sandy-clayey, prismatic-lumpy structure, not carbonated from hydrochloric acid, transition noticeable.

BC 54 - 70 variegated (5YR/4/4 and 5YR/6/4 in the dry state), moist, strongly compacted, medium sandy-clay, lighter than the above, unstructured, does not carbonate from hydrochloric acid.

The humus horizon has a thickness of 18-20 cm.

The soil texture in the surface horizon is clayey-sandy. The amount of physical clay is 17.2%. The soil texture in the illuvial horizon is medium sandy-clayey 39.7 to 42.1%. The amount of silt in the surface horizon is low, while in the illuvial horizon it is several times higher - 32.7 - 36.1%. The predominant fractions are those of silt, medium and fine sand. This soil texture determines poor water permeability, good water retention and unfavorable air regime. According to the amount of organic matter in the surface horizon, the soil is with

low humus content - 0.83%. They have a low reserve of total nitrogen and total phosphorus. Carbonates are not contained in the depth of the entire soil profile. The soil reaction has a strongly acidic pH in H₂O of 5 to 5.3. These soils have a number of unfavorable properties that make them suitable for a limited number of crops - very low humus content, sharp textural differentiation, strongly acidic soil reaction (it can be corrected by liming). They are suitable for growing some less demanding crops.

Eutric Planosols, moderately eroded

They occupy an area of 7688 da, 5.15 % of the total area southeast of the village of Dolna Banya. They are distributed mainly in the central flattened part of the territory of the farm units. They are formed on Pliocene and Tertiary deposits under the influence of forest vegetation. No significant erosion processes are observed in them. Their morphological structure can be observed by the description of a soil profile on a plateau in fruit orchard located 2 km north of Dolna Banya village (Yolevski, M. et al. 1974).

A₁E 0-29 Light gray-brown, fresh, loose, clayey-sandy, small crumble structure, powdery, not carbonated from hydrochloric acid, transition clear.

A₂B(t)g 29-42 light brown, fresh, compact, slightly sandy-clayey, crumble structure, partially dusted by pseudopodzolization, dusted with amorphous silica, not carbonated from hydrochloric acid, simple transition.

B₁(t)cg 42-75 light brown-reddish, moist, slightly dense, slightly sandy-clayey, prismatic, signs of gleying, contains manganese nodules of grains, does not carbonate from hydrochloric acid, transition gradual.

B₂(t)cg 75-115 brownish-reddish, moist, slightly dense, heavy sandy-clayey, prismatic, contains manganese nodules, does not foam from hydrochloric acid, transition noticeable.

C 115-140 light brownish-white, moist, compact, slightly sandy-clayey, unstructured, gravelly, slightly carbonated from hydrochloric acid.

Morphologically, these soils are characterized by weak (20-25 cm) humus horizon with light brown color and dusty from pseudopodzolization and processing small crumbly structure. Dusting with amorphous silica is observed here. Beneath it lies a deep about 70-100 cm alluvial horizon with a reddish dense color, clayey with a prismatic structure and the presence of manganese nodules on water-bearing parts, this horizon is less deep and contains unweathered rocks. Horizon C is almost intact Pliocene Tertiary deposits with light brown to off-white color. The terrain occupied by these soils is flat (with a slight slope) convenient for farm machines.

The soil texture in the surface horizon is clayey-sandy and the amount of physical clay is 18.4%. In the alluvial horizon the soil texture is sharply aggravated - the amount of physical clay is 51.1-62.8%.

The amount of silt in the upper two horizons is low while in the range of the illuvial horizon it is 45.6-57.4%. The predominant fraction of soil profile depth is that of silt followed by the fraction of medium and fine sand. The texture coefficient is 7.8.

This soil texture causes low water permeability, high water holding capacity and unfavorable air regime. The content of humus 0.94% in the surface horizon defines these soils as having low humus. In the lower divisions of the soil profile the amount of organic matter is insignificant - 0.36-0.5%. Carbonates are not contained in the depth of the entire soil

profile. The soil reaction is medium acidic in the surface horizon - pH 5.8 (H₂O). With good farming techniques some less demanding crops can be grown on these soils.

Eutric Fluvisols

They occupy an area of 2919 da - 1.96% of the total area.

They are formed on Alluvial-Deluvial deposits under the influence of meadow vegetation. They have a layered structure characteristic of all alluvial soils. The materials creating the individual layers have a light soil texture. Humus is better expressed in the upper part of the soil profile. The morphological structure of these soils is given by profile 2:

A_I 0-11 light gray-brown (7.5YR/5/6 in the dry state), fresh, loose, slightly sandy-clayey, weakly expressed fine-grained structure, does not carbonate from hydrochloric acid, transition noticeable.

A_{II} layer 11-24 grayish-brown (7.5YR/5/4 in the dry state), slightly moistened, loose, sandy (loose sand), unstructured, does not carbonate from hydrochloric acid, transition noticeable.

A_{III} layer 24-50 grayish-brown lighter than above (7.5YR/5/6 in the dry state), slightly moistened, loose, sandy (loose sand), unstructured, does not carbonate from hydrochloric acid.

The humus horizon has a thickness of 20-30 cm, the amount of organic matter in the humus horizon is 2.17-3.19%. The depth of the soil profile is 60-90 cm. Soil texture in the surface horizon is clay-sandy, the amount of physical clay is 20.1-28.5%. The predominant fractions are coarse particles. This soil texture determines very high water permeability, low water holding capacity and favorable air regime.

The soil reaction is moderately acidic to neutral pH in KCl with value of 5-5.7.

Leptic Cambisols, eroded, stony

Occupy an area of 15688 da - 10.5% of the total area of the study area. They are formed on weathering products on acid rocks under the influence of forest vegetation and active erosion. The profile of these soils is very short and the hard rock is closely laid. They have a light soil texture; they contain a high percentage of skeletal material and a small percentage of organic matter. Due to the very large slope occupied by these soils they are almost economically irrelevant since only individual sections are used.

Our research is based on the analysis of soil samples from the area representing the natural meadow (profile 1), winter cereal - rye (profile 2) with raspberry plantations (profile 2) and left in the prologue, after some years of use (profile 3).

Researched indicators:

Physical and textural parameters:

- soil texture - by pyrophosphate method (by Kaczynski, 1958);
- structure and waterproof aggregates - by sieve analysis dry and wet sieving by the method of NI Savinov (Penkov et al. 1997).

*Agrochemical indicators:

- mobile forms: nitrogen - by the method of Bremner and Kiney; phosphorus - by the method of P. Ivanov; potassium - P. Ivanov (Penkov et al. 1997);
- humus - by the Turin method (Kononova, 1963);
- pH - potentiometrically (in water and in potassium chloride), (Penkov et al. 1997);
- carbonate content - by the Scheibler method (Penkov et al. 1997).

An agrotechnical assessment was performed for the condition of the production areas subject to the study - soil condition in the humus horizon, presence of plant residues, weed density, etc.

Results and Discussion

From the comparative analysis of the results of the laboratory determination of the soil texture, changes in the fractional composition of all studied soil differences are established. For a period of over fifty years, depending on the land use, microrelief and the influence of meteorological conditions, the changes in the main soil horizons are more or less distinctive.

Table 1. Soil texture profile 1 and 54 Dystric Planosols

Horizon and depth (cm)	1.00 - 0.25	0.25 - 0.05	0.05 - 0.01	0.01 - 0.005	0.005 - 0.001	<0.001	Σ <0.01
profile 54							
A ₁ 0-20*	43.2	27.1	11.4	1.9	3.9	11.4	17.2
B _{1t_g} - 20-36*	23.6	24.6	8.4	2.6	3.4	36.1	42.1
B _{2t_g} - 36-54*	23.7	25.6	9.2	2.7	4.3	32.7	39.7
profile 1							
A ₁ -0-20**	39.6	30.8	13.5	2.5	3.1	10.6	16.2
B _{1t_g} -20-36**	29.9	25.7	9.3	2.8	2.9	34.8	40.5
B _{2t_g} -36-54**	29.7	26.3	10.7	2.6	6.1	22.7	31.4

* Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 1974, Yolevski, M., et al. „Soil characteristics of the land of Dolna Banya – Sofia district, archive of IP ”N. Pushkarov”, Sofia.

** Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 2019.

A comparative analysis of the data on the soil texture of Dystric Planosols shows that despite the long-term difference between the two studies, the fluctuations in the fractional composition are insignificant (profile 1).

The long-term impact and sporadic production activity on the land plot did not significantly affect the soil texture of the soil distinction. In the surface horizon, the silt and physical clay content was almost unchanged for the long period between the two analyzes. More significant differences between the fractional composition were found in the B₂ horizon. The content of the silty fraction decreases sharply - by 10%, and the content of physical clay decreases by 8%. Probably in the C horizon there is a porous rock mass in which parts of the fine fractions of the clay have deposited.

Of note is the fact that as a result of the absence of land use the humus content increases - on average by 0.09%. The inclusion of the area in the production activity was for a short time and did not create a risk of surface water erosion.

When comparing the data available from the soil outline and those of made agrochemical analysis indicated that the mobile forms of nitrogen in arable layers is reduced to 4-5 mg / kg soil, and that of useful phosphorus 2.5 times. There is an increase in the useful forms of potassium in the surface horizon, probably due to the decomposition of straw from cultivated cereals. The reaction of the soil solution remains moderately acidic in the surface horizon, but in the B horizon it becomes slightly acidic.

Table 2. Agrochemical properties profile 1 and profile 54 Dystric Planosols.

Horizon and depth (cm)	pH		Carbonates (CaCO ₃)	Base Saturation (V%)	mg / kg	mg / 100 g		Humus %
	H ₂ O	KCL			Total digest. N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	
profile № 54								
A ₁ 0-20*	5.0	4.1	0,0	65.6	19, 1	5.6	16.8	0.83
B _{1t_g} 20-36*	5.3	4.3	0,0	66.3	15.5	1.1	18.0	0.77
B _{2t_g} 36-54*	5.1	4.2	0,0	71.4	10.0	0.6	15.9	0.54
profile № 1								
A ₁ 0-20**	5.3	4.3	0,0	62.0	14.2	2.3	22.0	0.88
B _{1t_g} 20-36**	5.5	4.6	0,0	68.4	11.7	0.2	13.3	0.86
B _{2t_g} 36-54**	5.5	4.5	0,0	-	-	-	-	-

* Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 1974, Yolevski, M., et al. „Soil characteristics of the land of Dolna Banya – Sofia district, archive of IP ”N. Pushkarov”, Sofia.

** Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 2019.

During the long period between the two studies, profile 2 revealed significant changes in horizons A and B, which are a consequence of the impact of climatic factors and its inclusion in the land fund. Due to the application of a crop rotation system of agriculture through the alternation of cereals oats and rye and trench flax and potatoes, the unification of the soil texture at a depth of up to 42 m is established.

Table 3. Soil texture profile 2 and profile 4 Eutric Planosols.

Horizon depth (cm)	Hygr. moisture %	> 1	1- 0.25	0.25- 0.05	0.05- 0.01	0.01- 0.005	0.005- 0.001	<0.001	Σ <0.01
Profile 4									
AE 0-29*	1.93	0.1	31.6	29.9	18.7	4.1	7	7.3	18.4
A ₂ B _g 29-42*	4.40	1.4	38.3	16.2	13.6	6.9	5.2	15.1	27.2
B _{t_g} 42-75*	-	0	13.2	13.6	7.9	2.5	2.9	57.4	62.8
Profile 2									
AE 0-29 **	3.05	0.0	36.8	37.3	4.9	5.3	6.9	8.8	21
A ₂ B _g 29-42 **	5.36	0.0	37.1	35.6	5.0	5.7	6.5	10.1	22.3
B _{t_g} 42-75 **	-	0.0	5.2	17.4	25.3	10.6	5.3	39.9	55.8
Profile 2									
AE 0-29 ***		0.0	31.4	40.1	5.4	5.9	6.8	10.4	23.1
A ₂ B _g 29-42***		0.0	31.8	37.9	2.1	5.9	8.9	13.4	28.2
B _{t_g} 42-75***		0.0	9.1	15.5	21.8	12.8	7.1	41.4	61.3

* Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 1974, Yolevski, M., et al. „Soil characteristics of the land of Dolna Banya – Sofia district, archive of IP ”N. Pushkarov”, Sofia.

** Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 2019 from levels with three crop rotation

*** Note - the data are from the analysis of samples 2019 perennial plantation - raspberries

Unlike the initial data, where the process of pseudopodzolization is visibly outlined in the three horizons, in the analysis in 2019 there is a visible textural boundary between A and B horizon, as the content of silt is 4.5 times higher and physical clay over 3 times. In land use with perennial plantations - raspberries, a higher content of silt and physical clay is found in

the A₂B horizon, as compared to the levels with predominant cultivation of cereals and cereal-legume mixtures, the physical clay has a 5% increase. A probable reason is the fact that during the creation of the raspberry plantation deep plowing was performed, followed by plowing in the rows every year while during the three-field crop rotation the depth of cultivation is up to 20 cm.

The chemical properties data for the two surface horizons outline some trends. The reaction of the soil solution of weakly acidic to neutral after long period becomes moderately acid (5.5-6.2 in H₂O). This change is due to natural acidification processes under the influence of water from the adjacent forest vegetation and not from production activity. The land section has been artificial meadow, which then becomes a natural grass. The soil is depleting of bases in the surface horizon, despite the percentage increases in the depth, reaching 78.0%.

Table 4. Chemical properties Profile № 2 and Profile № 4 Eutric Planosols

Horizon and depth (cm)	pH		Carbonates (CaCO ₃)	Base Saturation (V%)	mg/kg	mg/100 g		Humus %
	H ₂ O	KCL			Total N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	
Profile 4								
AE 0-29*	5.8	5.0	0.0	65.6	18.0	8.3	22.6	0.94
A ₂ Bg 29 – 42*	6.7	5.7	0.0	70.4	16.2	5.4	19.7	0.5
Btg 42 -75*	6.5	5.6	0.0	77.0	9.6	1.2	14.8	0.43
Profile 2								
AE 0-29 **	5.5	4.7	0.0	55.7	16.6	1.8	19.0	1.05
A ₂ Bg 29 – 42**	6.2	5.2	0.0	78.0	12.0	0.2	15.6	0.68
Btg 42 -75**	-	-	0.0	-	-	-	-	-
Profile 2								
AE 0-29 ***	5.8	4.9	0.0	62.8	25.3	3.0	20.1	1.01
A ₂ B 29 – 42***	6.3	5.5	0.0	65.0	20.5	0.6	16.8	0.68
Btg 42 -75***	-	-	0.0	-	-	-	-	-

* Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 1974, Yolevski, M., et al. „Soil characteristics of the land of Dolna Banya – Sofia district, archive of IP ”N. Pushkarov”, Sofia.

** The data are from the analysis of soil sample from 2019 from a field with three crops rotation

*** The data are from the analysis of soil sample from 2019 with permanent crop raspberries

During the long-term land use of the area it is established that during the raspberry plantation the assimilable forms of nitrogen increase, as for the horizons to a depth of 42 cm it is respectively 5.8 mg/kg of soil. In the absence of balanced fertilization, the mobile forms of phosphorus and potassium decrease and it is more significant for the amount of P₂O₅- 4.5 times in the area with three crop rotation and about 3 times in the area occupied by raspberries. We assume that when creating the perennial plantation, basic fertilization with phosphorus and potassium was performed.

Pseudopodzolic soils differences, in addition to a pronounced textural differentiation, are also characterized by a weak humus horizon and an acid reaction of the soil solution (Koynov et al., 1972). The treatment of these soils should be carried out during time of appropriate humidity to avoid some adverse physical and mechanical consequences. The arable land can be deepened to 25-30 cm with the application of manure and higher doses of

mineral fertilizers. When using mineral fertilization priority should be given to fertilizers with physiologically alkaline actions.

The structure of the Fluvisols (Alluvial-Deluvial) soil is layered, with stratum which is formed under the influence of the flowing waters of the Maritsa River. Subsequently, the river withdrew to its current bed, and a process of deluvial formation began on the terrain. Of note is the fact that the percentage of coarse sand is increasing - by 15.7% and 21.8% respectively for A_I layer. and A_{II} layer. horizons.

Table 5. Soil texture profile № 3 and profile № 46 Eutric Fluvisols

Horizon depth (cm)	Hygr. moist ure %	Amount > 1	1- 0.25	0.25- 0.05	0.05- 0.01	0.01- 0.005	0.005- 0.001	<0.001	Σ <0.01
profile № 46									
A _I 0-11*	2.53	13.3	31.5	21.2	11.7	4.5	5.6	10	20.1
A _{II} 11-24*	5.20	42.7	33.1	18.2	0.5	1.5	1.9	11.9	15.3
A _{III} 24-50*	-	79.2	15.4	4.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	6.2	16.6
profile № 3									
A _I 0-11**	2.18	0.0	35.0	36.9	4.5	5.5	6.4	11.7	23.6
A _{II} 11-24**	2.60	0.0	32.2	40.0	3.7	5.5	6.4	12.2	24.1
A _{III} 24-50**	-	0.0	15.0	14.4	9.3	6.6	3.3	19.9	29.8

* Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 1974, Yolevski, M., et al. „Soil characteristics of the land of Dolna Banya – Sofia district, archive of IP ”N. Pushkarov”, Sofia.

** Note - the data are from the analysis of soil samples in 2019.

Based on microrelief, it can be assumed that this change in the soil texture is due to the surface water erosion with the adjacent land plot of asphalt road the soil was moved to declines forming the ravine of the river. A profile made in an adjacent pine grove gives grounds for such an assumption.

Table 6. Chemical properties profile 3 and profile 46 Eutric Fluvisols

Horizon and depth in cm	pH		Carbonates (CaCO ₃)	Base Saturation (V%)	Humus %
	H ₂ O	KCL			
profile 46					
A _I 0-11*	6.4	5.7	0.0	78.0	2.17
A _{II} 11-24*	6.7	6.0	0.0	76.6	1.45
A _{III} 24-50*	6.8	6.0	0.0	-	-
profile 3					
A _I 0-11**	6.1	5.2	0.0	67.3	1.78
A _{II} 11-24**	6.3	5.5	0.0	72.4	1.39
A _{III} 24-50**	6.7	-	0.0	-	-

* Note - the data are from the analysis of samples in 1974, Yolevski, M., et al. „Soil characteristics of the land of Dolna Banya – Sofia district, archive of IP ”N. Pushkarov”, Sofia.

** Note - the data are from the analysis of soil samples in 2019.

The chemical properties are characterized with slightly acidic to neutral pH in soil research in cooperative farm Dolna Banya which in 2019 showed a decrease to medium

acidic soil solution. Carbonates are washed deep into the profile and base saturation slightly decreased as a result of the impact of climatic factors. In the event of the water erosion the humus content is reduced of the Eutric Fluvisols, as for long-term decrease was respectively 0.39% and 0,06% for the first and second layer of the soil profile.

Conclusion

For a long period of time there were changes in the surface soil horizons of all studied differences of soils. The process of pseudopodzolization continues to develop in Planosols. It is observed an increase in the content of silt in the horizons located below the humus horizon. In the case of Eutric Fluvisols (Alluvial-Deluvial), an increase in the fraction of coarse and fine sand and a decrease in the humus content are reported. Land use has an impact on the soil texture in the case of moderately eroded Dystric Planosols. In the deeper horizons, when planted with raspberries, the content of silt and physical clay increases compared to the same soil difference in the area with the application of three crop rotation, compacted with cereals with a subsided surface. The content of mobile forms of nitrogen increases in the area with permanent planting. The useful for plants forms of phosphorus and potassium decrease more significantly in the area on which three crop rotation cultivated with cereals with a mouldboard ploughing for growing is applied.

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